

Interconnect Wires at the Nanoscale

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Introduction:

Scaling down dimensions increases the speed of transistors; However, this does not benefit interconnect wires.

As dimensions shrink, quantum effects like surface and grain boundary scattering cause an increase in resistivity, which leads to joule heating that makes them unreliable. Moreover, local interconnect delay increases significantly with the advancements of technology; this affects the overall performance of the circuit.

A Suggested Solution:

A possible solution is the use of 3D integrated circuits with thermal-aware layering. 3D ICs tackle the scaling problem by stacking 2D dies and connecting them in the 3rd dimension; this speeds up the connection between layered chips.

Benefits:

3D ICs promise significant benefits like shorter interconnects, more functionality fits into a smaller space; reduction in fabrication costs. In addition, 3D integration allows large numbers of vertical vias between the layers, which allows the construction of a wider bandwidth.

Challenges:

Although it is beneficial, it faces several challenges. Thermal Management is one of the biggest issues, because Heat building up within the stack must be dissipated.

Furthermore, taking full advantage of 3D ICs requires advanced design techniques and new CAD tools.

Reference:

[1] N. Srivastava and K. Banerjee, "Interconnect Challenges for Nanoscale Electronic Circuits," JOM, vol. 56, no. 10, pp. 30–31, Oct. 2004.